

WHEAT BREEDING USING TISSUE CULTURE TECHNOLOGY

Article Id: AL2021163

Sourik Poddar

Dept. of Genetics and Plant Breeding, Uttar Banga Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Pundibari,
Coochbehar, West Bengal, IndiaEmail: sourikpoddar@gmail.com

Plant tissue culture, as a method of growing explants extracted from the mother plant, is a good way to prepare a significant quantity of plant materials in a short period of time and boost natural levels of in vitro processing of useful compounds (Pandeb *et al.*, 2013). It has also encouraged researchers to advance their expertise in a variety of fields, including biology and molecular plant breeding. Plant cells and tissues' ability to respond optimally in tissue culture medium and later developmental stages may be beneficial in agriculture, horticulture, plant breeding, genetic engineering, and the chemical industry (Evans *et al.*, 2003).

Importance of Tissue Culture in Wheat

During the formation of callus in cereal tissue culture, the chemical 2,4-Dichlorophenoxy acetic acid is used to regulate growth (naturally synthetic auxin). Naqvi *et al.*, (2002) used a combination of 2,4-D and cytokinins to induce callus in wheat plants. When various doses of 2,4-D were used, different effects were observed on all genotypes (Elwafa and Ismail, 1999). The genotypes, forms of ex-plants, physiological state, geographical origin, culture mediums, and their interactions all influence the callogenesis and organogenesis responses of tissue culture techniques in wheat plants (Chen *et al.*, 2006).

Mature Embryo Culture in Wheat

Mature embryo cultures revealed significant variations in wheat cultivars in terms of plant regeneration and callus effectiveness (Zale *et al.*, 2004). In wheat, mature embryos with or without endosperm were used to form calluses and regenerate plants. Embryogenic callus proportion was shown to be higher in endosperm-free embryos (Turhan and Baser, 2004). At a rate of 1.28% to 1.77 %, mature embryos cultured in *Triticum aestivum* and *Triticum durum* result in the growth of transgenic plants (Patnaik *et al.*, 2006).

Immature Embryo Culture in Wheat

Wheat callus reaction to ABA was demonstrated using immature embryo culture (Morris *et al.*, 1989). Immature embryo culture can be used to study the floral developmental mechanisms in wheat. Immature embryos are the best ex-plant sites for callus induction and somatic embryogenesis in cereals. Immature embryos cultured in wheat can quickly produce callogenesis and organogenesis (Redway *et al.*, 1990).

Somaclonal Variations in Wheat

Plant regeneration from embryogenic tissues of somatic cells revealed that morphological and chromosomal modifications occurred during culturing as well. Variations in Mt DNA plantlets were observed in immature embryo culturing, and these distinctions were easily stabilised during Callogenesis (Hartmann *et al.*, 1987). Variations in Mt DNA were also observed in green plant regeneration arising from somatic tissue culture (Aubry *et al.*, 1989). Plants that have undergone in-vitro culturing have phenotypic modifications that are real representations of genetic variants (Liu and Chen, 1978 a and b; Orton, 1980). Some plants retained their original morphology, demonstrating that changes in field conditions are caused by physiological factors rather than genetics (Callebaut *et al.*, 1978)

Conclusion

Plant Tissue Culture has a major impact on both agricultural and ornamental plants. In-vitro embryo culture can help with a variety of realistic plant breeding issues. Embryo culture may aid in the research of plant feeding, metabolism, and developmental stages. Somatic embryogenesis, cell biological techniques, and molecular approaches, in addition to traditional breeding programs, have been shown to be useful instruments for improving the genetics of various crop plants. Callus induction and plantlet regeneration is greatly influenced by media structure, genotype, and their interactions. The regeneration capability of media can be increased by using various growth regulators.

Reference

Aubry C.J., Buyser D., Hartmann C., Henry Y., and Rode A., 1989, Changes in molecular organization of mitochondrial genome in albino tissue cultures derived from wheat pollen embryos and in plants regenerated from these cultures, *Plant Science*, 65(1): 103-110

Callebaut A., Motle J.C., and Cat W.D., 1987, Substrate utilization by embryogenic and non-embryogenic cell suspension cultures of (*Cucumis sativus* L.), *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 127(3-4): 271-280

Chen J.Y., Yue R.Q., Xu H.X., and Chen X., 2006, Study on plant regeneration of wheat mature embryo under endosperm- supported culture, *Agriculture Sciences in China*, 5(8): 572-578

Elwafa A.A.A., and Ismail A.E.A., 1999, Callus induction and plant regeneration from cultures of immature embryos of spring wheat, *Assiut J. Agric. Sci.*, 30: 13-23

Evans D.E., Coleman J.O.D., and Kearns A., eds., 2003, *Plant Cell Culture*, Bios Scientific Publishers, Taylor and Francis Group, London, pp.1

Hartmann C., Buysers J.D., Henry Y., Falconet D., Lejeune B., Benslimane A., Quettera F., and Rode A., 1987, Time course of mitochondrial genome variation in wheat embryogenic somatic tissue cultures, *Plant Science*, 53(2): 191-198

Liu M.C., and Chen W.H., 1978a, Tissue and cell culture as aid to sugarcane breeding II. Performance and yield potential of sugarcane callus derived lines, *Euphytica*, 25(1): 273-282

Liu M.C., and Chen W.H., 1978b, Significant improvement in sugarcane by using tissue culture methods, In: Fourth International Congress Plant Tissue and Cell Culture (Abstr.) Univ. Calgary, Alberta, Canada, pp.163

Morris C.F., Moffatt J. M., Sears R.G., and Paulsen G.M., 1989, Seed dormancy and responses of caryopses, embryos, and calli to abscisic acid in wheat, *Journal of Cancer*, 90(2): 643-647

Naqvi S.M.S., Yasmin T., Rashid H., Chaudary Z., and Qureshi A., 2002, Callus induction from seeds of *Zea mays* var. EV-2097, *Pakistan Journal of Biological Science*, 5(9): 956-958

Orton T.J., 1980, Chromosomal variability in tissue cultures and regenerated plants of *Hordeum*, *Theoretical & Applied Genetics*, 56(56): 101-112

Pande S.S., and Gupta P., 2013, Plant tissue culture of *Stevia rebaudiana* (Bertoni): A review, *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*, 5(1): 26-33

Patnaik D., Vishnudasan D., and Khurana P., 2006, Agrobacterium mediated transformation of mature embryos of *Triticumaestivum* and *Triticum durum*, *Current Science*, 91(3): 307-317

Redway F.A., Vasil V., Vasil I.K., 1990, Characterization and regeneration of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) embryogenic cell suspension cultures, *Plant Cell Reports*, 8(2): 714-717

Turhan H., and Baser I., 2004, Callus induction from mature embryo of winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), *Asian Journal of Plant Sciences*, 73(7): 17-19

Zale J. M., Borchardt-wier H., Kidwell K.K., and Steber C.M., 2004, Callus induction and plant regeneration from mature embryos of a diverse set of wheat genotypes, *Plant Cell tissue and organ culture*, 76(76): 277-281